

Structural Analysis of Samarium Substitution on Nanocrystalline Nickel Ferrite

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Abstract

Nickel ferrite being one of the most important inverse spinel ferrite has a wide range of applications especially as microwave devices. Rare earth also makes possible the high technology world we live in today. So, Samarium, a rare earth metal, is used as a dopant material with various ratios along with the Nickel ferrite in this research. A series of Samarium substituted Nickel ferrites $\text{Ni}(\text{Sm}_x\text{Fe}_{1-x})_2\text{O}_4$ with molar ratio ($x=0.0000, 0.0125, 0.0250, 0.0375, \text{ and } 0.0500$) have been synthesized by the conventional solid-state reaction method. The elemental compositions of the starting materials have been studied by Energy Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence (EDXRF) and X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) Methods. The powders have been pre-sintered at 1000°C for 4 h and have been characterized by XRD. XRD analysis reveals that the samples are single phase inverse spinel cubic structure with crystallize sizes in the range of 33.94 nm to 47.87 nm. X-ray densities are in the range of 5.30 g/cm^3 to 5.50 g/cm^3 . The results can be explained on the basis of composition.

Keywords: Nickel ferrite, conventional solid-state reaction method, EDXRF, XRD

Introduction

Nanosized spinel ferrite particles have attracted much attention in recent years because of their potential applications in high density magnetic recording, magnetic fluids, spintronics, data storage and gas sensors [Veena Gopalan, et al., 2009 and Mathew George, et al., 2006]. Among the ferrite nanoparticles, nickel ferrite has been widely studied due to its excellent chemical stability, mechanical hardness, reasonable saturation magnetization and high magneto-crystalline anisotropy [Yue Zhang, et al., 2010]. These properties make it a promising candidate for many applications, such as magnetic data storage, magnetic drug targeting, biosensors and magnetic refrigeration. Largest application of suppression ferrites are in industrial, computer and telecom. [Zhenfa Zi, et al., 2009].

Nano ferrites are simultaneously good magnetic and dielectric materials. The properties of ferrites are sensitive to synthesis method, synthesis conditions, synthesis parameters, nature and type of substitution and cation distribution. Ferrites are very important and widely used materials in technical designing and applications at high frequencies. The interesting physical and chemical properties of the ferrites arise from their ability to distribute the cations among the tetrahedral (A) and Octahedral (B) sites [Blasse, G.]. In order to achieve a high degree of molecular mixing, chemical homogeneity, control of stoichiometry, low calcination and sintering temperature/ time, various chemical methods have been used for the synthesis of spinel ferrites [Kawade, et al., 2000 and Gopalan, et al., 2009].

Crystal Structure of Ferrite

Ferrites are ferromagnetic materials having iron oxide as their main component along with the metal oxides. Ferrites based on the basis of crystal structure are mainly divided into three groups namely spinel ferrites, garnets and hexa-ferrite. The applications of these are different due to their crystal structure. All these types of ferrites are equally important from the point of view of their application and therefore they are widely studied by many researchers

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[Blasse, G and Thankachan, S., 2013]. Spinel ferrites having the general formula MeFe_2O_4 in which Me and Fe display tetrahedral and octahedral cation sites respectively and O indicates the oxygen anion site. They are called cubic ferrites. In spinel ferrites, the relatively large oxygen anions form a cubic close packing with 1/2 of the octahedral and 1/8 of the tetrahedral interstitial sites occupied by metal ions. The unit cell of spinel ferrite belongs to the cubic structure and presents itself the cubic formed by $8\text{MeOFe}_2\text{O}_3$ molecules and consisting of 32 of O^{2-} anions. The oxygen anions form the close face-centered cubic (fcc) packing consisting in 64 tetrahedral (A) and 32 octahedral (B) empty spaces partly populated by Fe^{3+} and Me^{2+} cations [Toksha, et al., 2008 and Yoshida, et al., 2010]. A face centered cubic of 32 oxygen ions is formed with two kinds of interstitial sites (i) 64 tetrahedral sites surrounded by 4 oxygens (A sites) and (ii) 32 octahedral sites surrounded by 6 oxygens (B sites). Out of 64 tetrahedral, only 8 are occupied by cations and out of 32 octahedral, only 16 are occupied by cations as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of spinel structure showing tetrahedral and octahedral sites occupied by 'A' and 'B' structure.

Figure 2. EMI suppression cable fitting applications

Figure 3. Different shapes of ferrite

Energy Dispersive X – Ray Fluorescence Technology

Energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence technology (ED-XRF) provides one of the simplest, most accurate and most economic analytical methods for the determination of the chemical composition of many types of materials. It can be used for a wide range of elements, from sodium (11) to uranium (92), and provides detection limits at the sub-ppm level; it can also measure concentrations of up to 100% easily and simultaneously. It is non-destructive and reliable, requires no, or very little, sample preparation and is suitable for solid, liquid and powdered samples.

EDXRF spectrometers use a semiconductor material (an X-ray detector) to convert characteristic X-rays into electrical signals. The spectrometer's electronics digitize the signals produced by the detector, and send this information to a PC or internal electronics for display and analysis.

Photograph showing of the Energy Dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence Spectrometer (Shimadzu EDX 700) is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Energy Dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence Spectrometer (Shimadzu EDX 700)

X-ray Diffraction Technique

The X-ray fluorescence is a very useful technique. X-ray diffraction (XRD) is one of the most important non-destructive tools to analyze all kinds of matter ranging from fluids to powders and crystals. The applications of X-ray diffraction (XRD) include quantitative and qualitative phase analysis, crystallography, structure and relaxation determination, texture and residual stress investigation, control simple environment, micro-diffraction and nano-materials.

Powder pattern and structure can be described the d-spacing of lattice planes depend on the size of the elementary cell and determine the position of the peaks. The intensity of each peak is caused by the crystallographic structure, the position of the atoms within the elementary cell and their thermal vibration. The line width and shape of the peaks may be derived from conditions of measuring and properties-like particle size of the sample material. The crystallite size of the sample was estimated by using the Scherrer' formula,

$$D = 0.9\lambda / B \cos \theta \quad (1)$$

where, "D" is the crystallite size (nm), " λ " is the wavelength of incident X-ray (\AA), " θ " is the diffraction angle of the peak under consideration at FWHM (deg) and "B" is the Full Width at Half Maximum (radians).

In any crystalline material an infinite set of planes exists with different Miller indices, and each set of planes has a particular separation. For any set of planes there will be a diffraction maximum at a particular angle, θ . By combining the equation relating d_{hkl} to the lattice parameter for a particular system with the Bragg equation, a direct relationship between the diffraction angle and the lattice parameters can be derived. For example, for a cubic system, combining the geometric equation for a cubic system (where a is the lattice parameter):

$$\frac{1}{d^2} = \frac{h^2 + k^2 + l^2}{a^2} \quad (2)$$

with the Bragg equation

$$n\lambda = 2d \sin\theta \quad (3)$$

where $n = 1$ and rearranging for d gives

$$\frac{1}{d} = \frac{2 \sin \theta}{\lambda} \quad (4)$$

which means

$$\frac{1}{d^2} = \frac{4 \sin^2 \theta}{\lambda^2} \quad (5)$$

Substituting for $1/d^2$ in eqn (5) and rearranging gives

$$\sin^2 \theta = \frac{\lambda^2}{4a^2} (h^2 + k^2 + l^2) \quad (6)$$

By using this equation, structural information about the crystals under study can be obtained [Thankachan, et al., 2013].

And then, the X-ray density is

$$d_x = \frac{nM}{a^3 N} \text{ [g/cm}^3\text{]} \quad (7)$$

Where M = molecular weight of the sample

n = number of molecules in a unit cell of spinel lattice

a = lattice parameter and

N = Avogadro number.

The Volume of the Unit Cell $V = a^3$ [Sun, Z., et al., 2009]

Photograph showing the front-panel of the RIGAKU MULTIFLEX X-Ray diffractometer is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. The RIGAKU, MULTIFLEX powder X-ray Diffractometer

Rare Earth Elements

The Japanese calls rare earth elements as “the seeds of technology.” The US Department of Energy calls them [“technology metals.”](#) They make possible the high technology world we live in today. They are the elements that have become irreplaceable to our world of technology. With rare earths, a little goes a long way. While the amount of rare earths in each phone is very small, the quantity of phones sold each year is impressive.

Rare earth elements are a set of seventeen chemical elements in the periodic table 1, specifically the fifteen lanthanides with the atomic numbers 57 to 71 plus scandium which has atomic number 21 as well as Yttrium with atomic number 39. Scandium and yttrium are considered rare earth elements since they tend to occur in the same ore deposits as the lanthanides and exhibit similar chemical properties. All 17 of these elements occur together. Since their physical and chemical properties are also very similar they are difficult to separate. The 17 rare earth elements are divided into two groups. The Light Rare Earth Elements (LREE) are those with atomic numbers 57 through 63 (lanthanum to europium). The Heavy Rare Earth Elements (HREE) have atomic numbers from 64 to 71 (gadolinium to lutetium). Scandium and yttrium have properties similar to the heavy rare earths and are included within this group.

Rare earth metals and alloys that contain them are used in many devices that people use every day such as computer memory, DVDs, rechargeable batteries, cell phones, magnets, fluorescent lighting and much more.

Many rechargeable batteries are made with rare earth compounds. Demand for the batteries is being driven by demand for portable electronic devices such as cell phones, readers, portable computers, and cameras. Some of Rare earth elements are shown in Figure 6.

Table 1. Rare Earth Elements Periodic table

Rare Earth Elements																					
by Geology.com																					
H																	He				
Li	Be															B	C	N	O	F	Ne
Na	Mg															Al	Si	P	S	Cl	Ar
K	Ca	Sc	Ti	V	Cr	Mn	Fe	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Ga	Ge	As	Se	Br	Kr				
Rb	Sr	Y	Zr	Nb	Mo	Tc	Ru	Rh	Pd	Ag	Cd	In	Sn	Sb	Te	I	Xe				
Cs	Ba	La-Lu	Hf	Ta	W	Re	Os	Ir	Pt	Au	Hg	Tl	Pb	Bi	Po	At	Rn				
Fr	Ra	Ac-Lr	Rf	Db	Sg	Bh	Hs	Mt													
Lanthanides																					
La Ce Pr Nd Pm Sm Eu Gd Tb Dy Ho Er Tm Yb Lu																					
Actinides																					
Ac Th Pa U Np Pu Am Cm Bk Cf Es Fm Md No Lr																					

Figure 6. Some of Rare earth elements

	<p>Rare earth magnets are used in wind turbines. Some large turbines require two TONS of rare earth magnets. These magnets are very strong and make the turbines highly efficient. Rare earth magnets are used in turbines and generators in many alternative energy applications.</p>
	<p>Every hybrid-electric and electric vehicle has a large battery. Each battery is made using several pounds of rare earth compounds. The use of electric vehicles is expected to increase rapidly, driven by energy independence, climate change and other concerns. This will increase the demand for rare earth materials.</p>
	<p>Tiny amounts of rare earth metals are used in most small electronic devices. These devices have a short lifespan, and REE recycling is infrequently done.</p>

Figure 7. Uses of Rare earth elements

Experimental Procedure

A series of Samarium substituted nano ferrites having the chemical formula $\text{Ni}(\text{Sm}_x\text{Fe}_{1-x})_2\text{O}_4$ with molar ratio ($x = 0.0000, 0.0125, 0.0250, 0.0375, \text{ and } 0.0500$) has been prepared by conventional solid-state reaction method. The starting raw materials for the synthesis process were Nickel Oxide [NiO], Ferric Oxide [Fe_2O_3], Samarium Oxide [Sm_2O_3]. Firstly, the elemental concentration of the raw materials has been characterized by using the Energy Dispersive X-Ray Fluorescence Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu EDX 700). All chemical in this work from stoichiometric amounts of high-purity NiO and Fe_2O_3 (Sigma-Aldrich > 99.99%) were used as raw material. The required amount of the NiO, Fe_2O_3 and Sm_2O_3 has been weighed with digital balance. And then, they have been mixed in an A-gate motor and grounded for 4 h to be homogeneous mixture. The mixture has been pre-sintered at 1000°C for 4 h in a furnace with heating rate of $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and cooled to room temperature with the same rate and cooled to room temperature to obtain spinel phase. After that, that sample has been ground with an A-gate motor for 1 h. And the crystallographic structure of nickel ferrite powder has been investigated by X-ray powder diffraction analysis using RIGAKU MULTIFLEX X-ray diffractometer. The flow chat of the sample preparation for the formation of samarium substituted nickel ferrite is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Flow chart of the sample preparation of Samarium substituted Nickel ferrite

Figure 9. Procedure for the sample preparation of Samarium substituted Nickel ferrite

Figure 12. The XRD spectrum of raw material NiO

Figure 13. The XRD spectrum of raw material Fe₂O₃

Materials and Methods

Samarium substituted Nickel Ferrites $\text{Ni}(\text{Sm}_x\text{Fe}_{1-x})_2\text{O}_4$ with molar ratio ($x = 0.0000, 0.0125, 0.0250, 0.0375$ and 0.0500) have been synthesized by Solid State Method involving pre-sintering temperature at 1000°C for 4 h. In the reference papers, the other researchers prepared the samples with the pre-sintered temperatures of 900°C , 950°C and 1000°C for 4 h. The result of XRD patterns was approved that the formation of single phase cubic spinel structure and is more optimized at about the temperature 1000°C [Ei, P P K., 2015]. Therefore, in this synthesis the pre-sintered temperature has been used 1000°C for 4 h.

Phase Identification on Pre-sintered Sample

XRD patterns of Samarium substituted nickel ferrite are shown in Figure 14 to Figure 18. The steps of preparation for the samarium substituted nickel ferrite from $x = 0.0000$ to $x = 0.0500$ are shown in Figure 19. XRD pattern shows that the sample belongs to inverse spinel cubic structure. The average lattice parameters of the samples are obtained between 8.3389 \AA and 8.3885 \AA . The average crystallite sizes of the samples were obtained in the range of 33.94 nm to 51.04 nm which indicates the nano crystallite size. Lattice parameters increase and experimental densities of the prepared sample also increase with composition of samarium. Values of Crystallite size, lattice parameters, X-ray densities and unit cell volumes of all the samples are given in the Table 4. The Crystallite size and density of $\text{Ni}(\text{Sm}_x\text{Fe}_{1-x})_2\text{O}_4$ ferrite with different Sm content (x) curves are shown in Figure 20 and Figure 21.

Figure 14. The XRD spectrum of pre-sintering sample $\text{Ni}(\text{Sm}_x\text{Fe}_{1-x})_2\text{O}_4$ with ($x = 0.0000$)

Figure 15. The XRD spectrum of pre-sintering sample $\text{Ni}(\text{Sm}_x\text{Fe}_{1-x})_2\text{O}_4$ with ($x = 0.0125$)

Figure 16. The XRD spectrum of pre-sintering sample $\text{Ni}(\text{Sm}_x\text{Fe}_{1-x})_2\text{O}_4$ with ($x = 0.0250$)

Figure 17. The XRD spectrum of pre-sintering sample Ni (Sm_x Fe_{1-x})₂ O₄ with (x = 0.0375)

Figure 18. The XRD spectrum of pre-sintering sample Ni (Sm_x Fe_{1-x})₂ O₄ with (x = 0.0500)

Figure 19. The XRD spectrum of pre-sintering sample Ni (Sm_x Fe_{1-x})₂ O₄ with (x = 0.0000, 0.0125, 0.0250, 0.0375 & 0.0500)

Table 4. Crystalline size, Lattice Parameter, X-ray density & Unit cell volume

No	Samples	Mol.wt (g/mol)	Crystallite size(nm)	Lattice constant(Å)	X-ray density (g/cm ³)	Volume (Å) ³
1	Ni Fe ₂ O ₄	234.38	42.40	8.3845	5.30	588.08
2	Ni(Sm _{0.0125} Fe _{0.9875}) ₂ O ₄	236.74	33.94	8.3768	5.35	587.81
3	Ni(Sm _{0.0250} Fe _{0.9750}) ₂ O ₄	239.11	47.87	8.3389	5.48	579.86
4	Ni(Sm _{0.0375} Fe _{0.9625}) ₂ O ₄	241.47	45.88	8.3531	5.50	582.83
5	Ni(Sm _{0.0500} Fe _{0.9500}) ₂ O ₄	243.83	36.52	8.3885	5.49	590.27

Figure 20. Crystallite size of $\text{Ni}(\text{Sm}_x\text{Fe}_{1-x})_2\text{O}_4$ ferrite with different Sm content (x)

Figure 21. Density of $\text{Ni}(\text{Sm}_x\text{Fe}_{1-x})_2\text{O}_4$ ferrite with different Sm content (x)

Conclusion

Samarium substituted nickel ferrites have been initiated for the purpose of microwave applications. The magnetic ferrite, samarium substituted nickel nano crystallites have been successfully formed via Solid State Method involving pre-sintering temperature of 1000°C . XRD analysis reveals that the samples are single phase inverse spinel cubic structure with crystallite sizes in the range of 33.94 nm to 47.87 nm which indicates the formation of nano crystallite size. The average lattice parameters of the samples are obtained between 8.3389 \AA and 8.3885 \AA . The observed results can be explained on the basis of composition and crystallite size. Lattice parameters and crystallite sizes of the prepared sample are slightly random with the different compositions of samarium but the experimental densities are increase with the samarium content.

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References

- Blasse, G. (1964). *Philips Research Reports*. Suppl.3,
- Ei, P P K. (2015). *Study on The Effect of Rare-Earth Ions In Nickel Ferrite*.
- Gopalan, V. E., Kumar, S. D. & Anantharaman, M. R. (2009). On the structural, magnetic and electrical properties of sol-gel derived nanosized cobalt ferrite. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 485, 711 - 717.
- Kawade, V. B., Bichile, G. K., & Jadhav, K. M. (2000). *X-ray and Infrared Studies of Chromium Substituted Magnesium Ferrite*, 42, 33 – 37.
- Mathew George, Asha Mary John, Nair, Joy, S., & Anantharaman, A. M. R. (2006). Finitesize effects on the structural and magnetic properties of sol-gel synthesized NiFe₂O₄ powders. *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, 302, 190–195.
- Sun, Z. Zi, Yuh, X. & Song, W. (2009). Synthesis and magnetic properties of CoFe₂O₄ ferrite nanoparticles. *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, 321, 1251– 1257.
- Thankachan, S., Jacob, B. P., Xavier, S. & Mohammed, E. M. (2013). Effect of neodymium substitution on structural and magnetic properties of magnetic ferrite nanoparticles. *Physica Scripta*, 87, 025701 – 025707.
- Toksha, B. G., Shirsath, S. E., Patange, S. M. & Jadhav, K. M. (2008). Structural investigations and magnetic properties of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles prepared by sol-gel auto combustion method. *Solid State Communications*, 147, 479 – 483.
- Veena Gopalan, E., Joy, P. A., Al Omari, I. A., & Anantharaman M. R. (2009). *On the Structural, Magnetic and Electrical Properties of Sol-gel derived Nanosized Cobalt Ferrite*. 485, 711–717.
- Yoshida, Y., Gopalan, V. E., & Al-Omari, I. A. (2010). Inverse magnetocaloric effect in sol-gel derived nanosized cobalt ferrite. *Applied Physics A: Materials Science & Processing*, 99(2), 497 – 505.
- Yue Zhang, Zhi Yang, Di Yin, Yong Liu, & Chun Long Fei. (2010). *Composition and magnetic properties of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles prepared by the co-precipitation method*. 322, 3470–3475.
- Zhenfa Zi, Yuping Sun, & Wenhai Song. (2009). *Synthesis and magnetic properties of CoFe₂O₄ ferrite nanoparticles*. 321, 1251–1255.